

INCREASE CREATIVE THINKING BY TEACHING MATHEMATICS IN ELEMENTARY GRADES ON THE BASIS OF ADVANCED INTERNATIONAL EXPERIMENTS

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Abstract: The article provides a brief overview of the main problems of teaching mathematics, the development of creative activities of teachers by improving their mathematical thinking, the development of innovative educational methods for optimizing the educational process. The implementation of modern information technologies in education is aimed at organizing the form and means of education, as well as methods of providing assistance in the introduction of the system and Speed Adaptation in it.

Keywords: creative thinking, problematic, creative ability, competency approach, cognitive, collaborative

As an important strategic direction of the educational process in the developed countries of the world, developing the creative activity of the student by improving the mathematical thinking of the teachers, developing innovative educational methods for optimizing the educational process is the main part of teaching mathematics. is considered as one of the problems.

In the process of developing the quality of education, globalization and integration of education on a global scale, the issue of developing creative activity in mathematics among students is defined as one of the urgent tasks.

In our republic, effective work is being done to determine the strategic goals and priorities for the development of the field of pedagogical education, to develop the creative activity of students in mathematics, and to improve the quality of training of mathematics teachers who can work independently.

In the concept of development of the public education system until 2030, priority tasks such as "creating new generations of didactic materials and multimedia products for in-depth study of mathematics, popularizing the principles of improving students' mathematical literacy" are defined. Based on these tasks, it is important to determine the content of the development of creative creativity in students, to develop students' mathematical literacy, and to create a methodical system based on innovative educational technologies in teaching mathematics in general secondary schools.

In the development of social and economic relations in the 21st century, it is becoming more and more evident that human intelligence and spirituality are the main coordinating, developing factor and tool. Therefore, the education of a highly educated, morally rich, healthy, well-rounded generation is regulated by the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Policy Regarding Youth", "On Education" and "Personnel in accordance with the requirements of today's era, to educate young people who are competent in all aspects, who think independently, who are able to take responsibility for the future of our country, who are proactive, who mobilize all their potential for the benefit of the people, and who are intellectual and creative. created a solid legal framework for realizing its potential. From this point of view, it is important to teach students excellent knowledge, skills and abilities in mastering subjects, and to define effective mechanisms and ways in this field.

In performing these tasks, he encourages primary school teachers to work on themselves, to do scientific and creative research, and to intellectually develop their pedagogical activities. Knowing the learning, processes, principles and laws related to the basics of elementary school mathematics allows the teacher to organize and manage the educational processes related to the school mathematics course in accordance with the requirements of the time. . This is the purpose of introducing the content of primary educational subjects, their teaching forms, methods, and tools in a mutually dependent manner, providing in-depth knowledge of primary educational subjects, their comprehensiveness Helping to mature as a developed person is the basis for the development of innovative activities. In primary education, innovative activities are carried out on the basis of subjective-subjective relations. This is the use of opportunities to clarify the components of the structure of cognitive and social competence-oriented activities of teachers' creative activity development, and to use the possibilities of sorting methodical sources and applying them in practice, based on the competence approach, an integrated methodical system of creative activity development (reproductive, creative research and innovation stages) improvement, innovative and integrated technologies, active methods (analytical, comparative, logical, independent work, problem-based research) and tools (didactic handouts, teaching-methodical manual) methodical system of developing teachers' creative activity requires improvement.

Based on didactics, we provide students with knowledge. We use different methods in the educational process. If we correctly choose the method of the lesson process correctly and successfully, the lesson will give a good result. It is

permissible to conduct each lesson with demonstration and technical means. Only then will the lesson be full of knowledge. The teacher should be inquisitive and conduct lessons in a variety of ways. In order for the lesson to be interesting, it is necessary to use not only visual aids, but also game elements, interesting and logical problems, and various didactic materials during the lesson.

Game elements can be used not only in class, but also in conference classes in extracurricular activities. It is definitely intended for elementary school students. At this age, they are more playful, easily bored, and distracted. We can attract them through the game.

Since elementary school students are young, it is necessary to teach them in simple language and to use game elements a lot in lessons. The main part of a student's life is played. Games are not only a didactic tool, they are the main form of a student's life. Therefore, we cannot solve the responsible tasks before us without mastering the finer points of the game and learning how to manage the game.

Special attention was paid to the fact that one of the important factors influencing the methods and means of developing creative abilities of primary school students is teacher-student cooperation. It is known that the educational process has a two-way character and consists of equal relations between the teacher and the students. The teacher who leads this process is responsible for the correct organization of the educational process, the correct implementation of educational goals and educational results. But this cannot be the basis for the birth of the wrong idea that the educational process is a process that takes place under the complete control of the teacher. The demand of the current era is to achieve a positive result with the help of a cooperative relationship, not by subjugating someone. It should not be forgotten that the formation of students' activities in the educational process is not only a mechanism for mastering the fundamentals of science, but also focuses on the formation of the general social and cultural abilities of a person.

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